

Learning-Based Animation Education in The Post-Covid Era at SMKN 2 Cimahi

Irvan Satrya Prana¹, Palupi Argani², Nanang Ganda Prawira³, Juju Masunah⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Faculty of Art Education and Design, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Animation learning at the vocational high school level in the last 5 years has experienced three paradigm changes in the teaching and learning process, namely offline learning before Covid-19, online learning during Covid-19 and blended learning in the post-Covid-19 period. This study aims to describe the conditions of animation learning with blended learning in the post-covid period in the Animation Study Program of SMKN 2 Cimahi. This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data collection techniques are carried out by interview and observation. The results of the study show that the results of learning with the blended learning method can improve students' animation skills better than during the learning period with the full online method.

KEYWORDS: animation, blended learning, post-covid learning, learning method, vocational school

I. BACKGROUND

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced educational institutions around the world to shift from face-to-face learning to fully online learning. This transition brings significant challenges, especially in vocational schools, where education relies heavily on hands-on practice. Animation education in vocational schools is one example, where students need practical skills that cannot be fully taught online. With the industrial revolution 5.0 giving birth to rapid innovation, this also has an impact on the field of education, namely education 5.0 where digital technology is used for continuous learning without being hindered by spatial and temporal boundaries (Imelda Nur Aryanti & Rusnilawati, 2022) . So that the implementation of blended learning offers a possible solution aimed at overcoming time and space limitations in face-to-face teaching (Li et al., 2023). And the strategy in blended learning significantly produces effective learning in improving student learning achievement and skills compared to conventional learning carried out by Yustina (Yustina et al., 2020)

Blended learning combines digital technology with direct interaction in the classroom, so that students can learn theory through online learning and apply those skills in face-to-face sessions in the laboratory. With the implementation of blended learning, it is hoped that students at SMKN 2 Cimahi can gain a more complete and comprehensive learning experience. This study aims to evaluate the implementation of blended learning at SMKN 2 Cimahi in the animation study program, identify the challenges faced, and evaluate the learning outcomes of blended learning compared to full online learning.

Figure 1. Blended learning method strategy

II. METHOD

This research uses a qualitative method approach, which is a procedure for research that produces descriptive data, usually in the form of writing about people or words from people or their visible behavior (Nursanjaya, 2021) as for the case study conducted at SMKN 2 Cimahi. Then for data collection techniques include:

- 1) Observation: Direct observation was conducted in the animation class to understand the dynamics of blended learning.
- 2) Interviews: Interviews were conducted with the head of the study program, productive teachers, and students from the animation study program to explore the challenges faced in implementing blended learning.
- 3) Analysis of Student Work: Students' animated works were analyzed to compare the outcomes of fully online learning with blended learning.

Data were analyzed descriptively to evaluate the challenges faced and the impact of blended learning on student learning outcomes.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of blended learning at SMKN 2 Cimahi combines online learning for theoretical materials and face-to-face for animation practice. However, the duration of face-to-face meetings is still limited due to infrastructure limitations. As a result, some practical skills cannot be trained in depth.

A) Technical and Non-Technical Constraints:

- 1) Technical Constraints: Many students have difficulty accessing technological devices such as laptops and stable internet, which hinders the online learning process.
- 2) Non-Technical Constraints: Student learning independence in online learning is still low. Many students are not yet accustomed to the independent learning model, so they need more intensive guidance from teachers.

B) School Initiative Program

Teachers suggest a computer installment program for students to improve access to technology. In addition, there needs to be a communication forum between schools, parents, and students to discuss the obstacles faced and solutions that can be applied in the implementation of blended learning.

1) Blended Learning

Driscoll (Ekayogi, 2023) states that there are four types of blended learning concepts, namely (1) Blended learning Blended learning is a learning method that combines various uses of technology in achieving goals. (2) Implementation of blended learning is a combination of various learning approaches such as behaviorism, constructivism, and cognitivism. (3) blended learning is a combination of various technologies, for example learning using video media, web, film and other media. (4) blended learning combines technology and tasks in creating a positive impact in the learning process.

2) Constructivism Theory

Constructivism theory is a theory that provides freedom for human activities to learn or seek needs with the ability to find desires or needs with the help of other people (Sugrah, 2020). Where this model teaches students the learning process begins with cognitive conflict activities, so that it is hoped that at the end of the learning process, students will gain knowledge that is built through the interactions contained within it with the environment (Romadhona et al., 2023). In blended learning, students can learn independently through online materials, which are then integrated with hands-on practice during face-to-face sessions. This strengthens their understanding of the material being studied.

3) Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework

Blended learning approach (blended learning) has been implemented by Garrison et al. (Garrison et al., 2000) developed the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework, which focuses on three main elements: cognitive presence, social presence, and teaching presence. (Geng et al., 2019). In the context of blended learning, these three elements work together to create a richer learning experience. Students learn not only from the material provided by the teacher, but also from interactions with their peers through online discussions and face-to-face meetings.

4) Teori Mastery Learning

Bloom (1968) developed the Mastery Learning theory, which emphasizes the importance of giving students enough time to master a concept before moving on to the next concept. In blended learning, the material learning model can

balance time-based learning flexibly because of its corrective path.(Winget & Persky, 2022) This approach can be implemented by utilizing the flexibility of time in online learning, where students can learn at their own pace and get the feedback needed to master the material.

C) Comparison of Learning Outcome

The results of the analysis show that students who take blended learning have better animation competencies compared to students who only learn through full online learning. Face-to-face practice helps students apply the theories learned online, especially in making 3D animations.

Figure 2. Create a 3d animation model in low poly mode in the form of a circus area park

The learning process carried out using blended learning in the image above, namely creating a 3D animation model in the form of a circus area with low poly mode, can be followed by all students in class XI and there has been an improvement, while for learning in class X which is carried out fully online, namely creating 2D animations, namely as in the following image 2, which aims to hone hand skills in the drawing process (nirmana).

Figure 3 make nirmana on A4 paper to hone hand skills

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Blended learning in the post-COVID-19 era is believed by education experts to be an ideal and effective method in improving the quality of learning. However, not all schools are in an ideal condition to implement it. SMKN 2 Cimahi, which is dominated by

students from lower-middle economic families, has difficulty in meeting blended learning needs, such as technological devices and internet access.

The school realizes the importance of implementing blended learning, both to enrich learning content and to anticipate the transformation of the world of work which is now widely adopting a remote work system. Schools are expected to make innovative breakthroughs, such as laptop installment programs and communication forums involving all stakeholders, so that the implementation of blended learning can run optimally.

Despite the various challenges, blended learning still needs to be continued considering its great benefits and potential for the future of education.

Improvement Technology Infrastructure in the area: There needs to be investment in technology infrastructure in schools, such as increasing internet access and providing computer devices for students who need them.

Learning sustainable for educator: Teachers need to receive further training on the use of learning technology, especially Learning Management Systems (LMS), to maximize the potential of blended learning.

Collaborate with Industry: SMKN 2 Cimahi can increase cooperation with the animation industry to provide more in-depth practical experience for students through internship programs or collaborative projects.

REFERENCES

1. Ekayogi, W. (2023). Blended Learning sebagai Upaya Mengatasi Learning Lost di Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Ikatan Keluarga Alumni Undiksha*, 21(1), 27–35. <https://doi.org/10.23887/ika.v>
2. Garrison, D., Anderson, T., & Archer, W. (2000). Critical Inquiry in a text-based environment. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 2(2), 87–105.
3. Geng, S., Law, K. M. Y., & Niu, B. (2019). Investigating self-directed learning and technology readiness in blending learning environment. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0147-0>
4. Imelda Nur Aryanti, & Rusnilawati. (2022). Model Blended Learning Berbantuan Video Animasi Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar IPA dan Sikap Kemandirian Siswa. *Jurnal Edutech Undiksha*, 10(2), 302–310. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jeu.v10i2.53529>
5. Li, M., Han, X., & Cheng, J. (2023). Handbook of Educational Reform Through Blended Learning. In *Handbook of Educational Reform through Blended Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-6269-3>
6. Nursanjaya. (2021). Understanding Qualitative Research Procedures: A Practical Guide to Make It Easier for Students. *Negotium: Journal of Business Administration Science*, 04(01), 126-141 (In Indonesia).
7. Romadhona, A. R., Prameita, A. E. D., Alvianita, M., Adha, E. A. W., & Iffah, J. D. N. (2023). Analisis Teori Belajar Konstruktivisme Dalam Pembelajaran Matematika Di Sma Budi Utomo Perak. *Laplace : Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika*, 6(1), 11–21. <https://doi.org/10.31537/laplace.v6i1.1097>
8. Sugrah, N. U. (2020). Implementasi teori belajar konstruktivisme dalam pembelajaran sains. *Humanika*, 19(2), 121–138. <https://doi.org/10.21831/hum.v19i2.29274>
9. Winget, M., & Persky, A. M. (2022). A Practical Review of Mastery Learning. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 86(10), 1114–1122. <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe8906>
10. Yustina, Syafii, W., & Vebrianto, R. (2020). The effects of blended learning and project-based learning on pre-service biology teachers' creative thinking skills through online learning in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 9(3), 408–420. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jpii.v9i3.24706>

Cite this Article: Prana, I.S., Argani, P., Prawira, N.G., Masunah, J. (2025). Learning-Based Animation Education in The Post-Covid Era at SMKN 2 Cimahi. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(7), pp. 3739-3742. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i7-62>